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Research Article

**THE EFFECT OF ETHICAL CLIMATE ON HEALTH CARE
STAFF'S COMPASSION****¹Umm-e-Habiba, ¹Kashif Khalil, ²Syeda Sidra Tasneem, ³Zunira Amir**¹Post RN, Nursing College, The Superior College Lahore, ²Director, Nursing College, The Superior College Lahore, ³Assitant Professor, Nursing College, The Superior College Lahore.**Article Received:** February 2019**Accepted:** March 2019**Published:** April 2019**Abstract:**

Ethical climate to the employee compassion in an organization has been acknowledged as a vital element for all nurses. Consequences related to ineffective climates such as decline in the quality of care, job dissatisfaction, stress and, role overload, and role ambiguity are potentially serious, not only for nurses and head nurses, but also their clients, colleagues, families and the entire organizations where they are employed.

The study aimed to explore ethical climate to the employee compassion between challenges among staff nurses of public hospitals and explore any relationship between the participants' demographics and their abilities to manage all the difficulties effectively. A quantitative, descriptive, co-relational research design was used to achieve the goals of this study. The total number of 109 staff nurse who agreed to participate in the study from selected public hospitals, Lahore, The Jinnah Hospital Lahore constituted of the study sample. Modified questionnaire was used to identify the ethical climate on the employee compassion has been created issues among staff nurse.

Keywords: *ethical climate, employee compassion, staff nurses, prioritization, resources, Technique.*

Corresponding author:**Umm-e-Habiba,**

Post RN, Nursing College, The Superior College Lahore.

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INTRODUCTION:

Ethical climate theory was first proposed by Victor and Cullen 1987, 1988 as cited by [1] and from that point onward has been exceptionally helpful in expanding our insight on an assortment of authoritative results, such as, working environment tormenting, authoritative responsibility, moral conduct, work fulfillment, and turnover goals, among different factors. In this study, we examine the surviving exploration of ethical climate to the employee compassion of nurses, so as to give comprehension of what has been watched up to this point, and what else [ECT] could be saddled towards looking at. Nurses are really compassionate with patient ,co-workers and subordinates but the gap of this study is to find out the problem that create by the attendants of the patients regarding defiance of resources like medicine , instruments, beds are less then patients ,and Intravenous fluid stands [2]. Ethical climates in hospitals are negatively increased day by day due to unavailable resources.

Direct caring and supportive behavior toward others, thereby facilitating patterns of compassion spirals [2]. For example, supervisors who feel that their organization values them and caress about their well-being are more likely to direct supportive behaviors toward their subordinates in nursing profession.

In different words, moral pioneers are probably going to be more notable as good examples when the setting has couple of moral signals.

Objectives

- To investigate the effects of ethical climate on employee compassion
- To find out the relationship between ethical climate and employee compassion

LITERATURE REVIEW

The previously mentioned benefits of compassion at work prompt a legitimate enthusiasm for distinguishing the hierarchical elements that can advance it[3].Especially, in cordiality industry settings, knowing why merciful activities happen is to a great degree of significant in advancing the help that individuals from work groups require from others to make group progress [4].

Since caring conduct can't be authorized at work, as it enormously surpasses part requests, the current research on empathy proposes that observing certain work environment conditions can make an outlook that empowers sympathy in associations [5]. Earlier research recommends various work conditions in which empathy is by and large liable to unfurl.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This study is conducted to assess the knowledge and attitude of the employee compassion on ethical climate.

Study design

A co-relational research design will be used for this study to assess the knowledge and attitude towards employee compassion on ethical climate in Jinnah hospital.

Setting

Setting of the study will be the organization of Jinnah hospital Molana Shokat Ali road Lahore.

Target population

My target population will be the Nursing employee of different departments the participants will be belong to different socioeconomic level and different demographical background, the participants will be male and female.

Sample Size and sampling techniques:

The data was collected through survey and the questioner was floated by the researcher herself. The 115 copies of questioner were circulated to employees of nursing departments [medical, surgical and emergency] and privet block unit 1 and record on the sport on SPSS version 20.Questioner were missing while 109 were valid.

Data Analysis:

Data analysis will be done by SPSS version 20. Statistical computer software for data analysis. This is a co-relational study and all the co-relational statistics will be obtained through the SPSS software

Including Criteria:

- ✓ Employees of different departments like emergency departments[medical, surgical]
- ✓ And other from private block
- ✓ Willing to participate
- ✓ Those who understands English

Excluding

- ✓ Employees of different departments
- ✓ Radiology, surgery, medicine ,oncology ,eye department ,ENT department ,urology department ,nephrology departments

Time Framework:

This study will approximately take 2-3 months.

Informed Consent:

Consents will be taken from all the participants and free hand will be given to the participants to take part in the study or refused to participate, participants will have also be the right to mentioned name or not.

Ethical consideration:

Enough information of research will be provided to participants with help of full consent and this will be achieved via a consent form attach to the questionnaire. Confidentiality will be considered by

informing participants. The right of participants will be protected by Nuremberg Code of Ethics.

Theoretical Framework:

Hypothesis:

H1: There is no significant relationship between ethical climate and employee compassion

H2: There is significant relationship between ethical climate and employee compassion

RESULTS:

Data analysis

The data analysis consists of three parts. The first part of data analysis is demographics which gives detail about demographic variables. Second part is descriptive analysis which provide us frequency and percentages of respondents regarding 20 items of questionnaire. Third part is regression test analysis which is used to check the relationship between the demographic characteristics of the staff nurses of Jinnah Hospital and employee compassion on ethical climate.

Part 1- Descriptive Analysis;

Table 1: Distribution of Staff nurses according to demographics

Table [1] depicts that the demographic characteristics of the participant. The table showed that [96.7%] participant of the study was female and only [3.7%] were male. Mostly participants 101[92.7%] belonged 25-35 years age group, 5[4.6%] were from 35-40 age group, 3[2.8%] were 18-25 years age group. Qualification is also part of demographics and 105[96.3%] participant was general nursing [Diploma], 4[3.7%] were 2-years BSN [Post RN], furthermore, 97[89%] participant were Single [unmarried], 12[11%] were married. Results indicates that around 108[99.1%] participants had 1-5yrs stay in organization and just 1[.9%] were having stay in organization.

Table: 1

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.597	10

Table 27: shows the result of reliability of Cronbach's Alpha is greater than 0.7% thus the results meets the standard requirement of reliability of employee compassion is a valid variable table mention or noted that

Table :2

Total Variance Explained

Component	Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.514	25.141	25.141
2	1.338	13.379	38.520
3	1.097	10.973	49.493
4	1.000	10.000	59.493

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table :3

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.687
Approx. Chi-Square	211.602
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Df
	45
	Sig.
	.000

Table 29 shows that instrument consist of one independent variable [ethical climate] and dependent variable [ethical compassion] has KMO values above 0.50 and Bartlett's test is significant[p=0.00] which meet the standard requirement .so, positive effect scale is valid.

Table: 3-0

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.541 ^a	.293	.286	.37469	.293	44.357	1	107	.000

This table shows that the total 29.3%[F=44.357] variations in the employee compassion is caused by ethical climate.

Table :3-1

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	6.870	1	6.870	44.357	.000 ^b
1 Residual	16.573	107	.155		
Total	23.443	108			

Table 31 shows that ANOVA is significant [P<0.05] and it represent research model is valid.

Table :4
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 [Constant]	1.519	.318		4.772	.000
Ethical Climate	.569	.085	.541	6.660	.000

Table 32 show that that ethical climate has significant effect on dependent variable. Further it shows that the one unit increase in the ethical climate cause the positive change of .569 in the employee's compassion.

TABLE 5

Groups	[Frequency] f	[Percentage] %
Gander		
Male	4	3.7
Female	105	96.3
Total	109	100
Age		
18-25Yrs	3	2.8
25-35Yrs	101	92.7
35-40Yrs	5	4.6
More than 50	0	0
Total	109	100
Qualification		
General Nursing diploma	105	96.3
Post RN BSN	4	3.7
Surgical Diploma	0	0
Other	109	100
Marital Status		
Married	12	11
Single	97	89
Total	109	100
Stay in Organization		
Less than 1Year	1	.9
1-5Years	108	99.1
6-10Years	0	0
Above 10Years	0	0
Total	109	100

DISCUSSION:

Ethical climate is a powerful tool for positive response and great performance in an organization of public hospital for the staff nurses. Ethical climate increase work satisfaction promotes conscience of team interest and social responsibility among the staff nurses [6]. In accordance with previous studies ethical climate has stronger impact on job satisfaction in work place and have a significant role for patient, co-workers and peers along with seniors. The purpose of the study is to find out the problems that occurred due to lack of resources in big city hospitals that have been created

ethical climate between staff nurses. Moreover, positive ethical environment should be maintained to subside the deviant behavior and establishing ethical infrastructure in a public hospital [3]. Lastly, awareness should be raised by campaign against ethical climate along with formal ethical system and informal ethical system is also important for the patient, peers, co-workers and subordinates.

The results of the current study reveal that there is positive significant relationship between ethical climate and nurse's compassion at the public hospitals of Lahore, Pakistan. Therefore, the hospitals'

administration should emphasize on the ethical issue and create the ethical climate to enhance the compassion among the employees which will ultimately become the reason of efficient health care system.

CONCLUSION:

The purpose of this study is to find out the problems regarding the ethical climate between staff nurses and develop the effective way to raise the compassion of the employees for the wellbeing of the public health care sector. The results reveal that there exists positive and significant relationship between ethical climate and employees' compassion among the public hospitals. Further studies should emphasize on the other factors which can raise the employee's compassion or may intervene the relationship of the ethical climate and employee's compassion.

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